

Exovedate

also known as “Eglise catholique, apostolique et vitale des Montagnes Lumineuses (Catholic, Apostolic, and Vital Church of the Bright Mountains)”

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** Supervised Entry, prepared from a literature review by a student or students under the direction of a Supervisor, typically as a classroom project; edited and vetted by Supervisor.*

Entry tags: Christian Traditions, Catholic, American Christianity, North American Religions, Religious Group, Abrahamic, 'Roman' Catholic

Exovedate was the term coined for a provisional government that attempted a Catholic state in the District of Saskatchewan by Louis Riel. Similar to movements that other scholars might call NRMs (new religious movements) and other 19th century sectarian movements, the group represented a new Catholic group that had separated from communion with Rome, part of a larger movement headed by Riel over the course of a decade. The group disbanded after a few months, but their actions have had a lasting impact on Canadian history and culture. Heavily influenced by ultramontanism and millenarianism, the group believed that Louis Riel was a prophet of God, and that the Catholic Church, namely the Roman papacy, was in decline. The belief was that God would soon show a dramatic sign, signaling the moving of the papacy so that it may be restored in Canada by the French-Canadians and the Métis. The papacy would move from Rome to Mount Royal in Montreal, Lower Canada (modern-day Quebec). Ignace Bourget, Bishop of Montreal, was thought to be the rightful pope. It was prophecized that this papacy would also become corrupt over time, at which point the papacy would move to St. Vital in Manitoba, where it would stay. The Exovedate sought to bring back the Mosaic Law as the foundation of its legal code, redistribute the land claimed by the Canadian government to various immigrant groups, convert all Jewish people to Christianity, and protect humanity from the evils of 'liberalism.' They believed this was all a to be done as a prelude to the Second Advent, which was prophecized by Riel to occur in 4209C.E. Group membership was known for certain to be a few dozen people, consisting of the government officials that made up the Exovedate and a few others close to Riel. The group died out after the North-West Rebellion in 1885, with the execution of its leader, Louis Riel.

Date Range: 1885 CE - 1885 CE

Region: District of Saskatchewan

Region tags: North America, Canada

The District of Saskatchewan at its greatest extent. The was the nation that was under briefly under the authority of the Exovedate during 1885. It would later be abolished, with parts of it being incorporated into the provinces of Alberta, Saskatchewan, and Manitoba.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: The Collected Writings of Louis Riel / Les écrits Complets De Louis Riel. 5 volumes. GEORGE F.G. STANLEY, General Editor. Volume Ditors: RAYMON DHUEL, GILLES MARTLEL, THOMAS FLANAGAN, GLEN CAMPBELL. Edmonton; The University of Alberta Press, 1985. Vol. 1 546pp. Vol. 2: 482 pp. Vol. 3 637 pp. Vol. 4 544 pp. Vol. 5 360 pp.
- Source 2: Riel, Louis and Thomas Flannigan. 1976. The Diaries of Louis Riel. Edmonton: Hurtig.
- Source 3: Flanagan, Thomas, desLibris - Books, and Canadian Publishers Collection. 1996. Louis 'David' Riel: Prophet of the New World. Rev. ed. Toronto: University of Toronto Press. doi:10.3138/9781442676824.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.thecanadianencyclopedia.ca/en/article/louis-riel>
- Source 1 Description: Encyclopedia article on Louis Riel, by George F.G. Stanley.
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.thecanadianencyclopedia.ca/en/article/metis>
- Source 2 Description: Encylclopedia articel on Métis by Adam Gaudry.
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.thecanadianencyclopedia.ca/en/article/north-west-rebellion>
- Source 3 Description: Encyclopedia articel on the North-West Resistance of 1885, the conflict that lead to the disbanding of the Exovedate and the execution of Louis Riel.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The Exovedate is itself an offshoot of Roman Catholicism, influenced by religious movements such as ultramontaniam and millenarianism. Making up the governmental body of the District of Saskatchewan, it came into contact with the various religious groups that inhabited North America during the late 1800's.

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

Notes: The vision Riel had for the Exovedate and his 'religion of the New World' would eventually lead to competitive cultural contact, within Christianity, and with outside religious groups, but the short-lived existence of the Exovedate means that competition never played out.

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

Notes: The religious creed of the Exovedate saw 'liberalism' in the late 1800's as an evil, particularly when it came to matters involving the Catholic Church. No official proclamation was made by the governmental body against liberalism or other religions, but Riel wrote about

prophecies concerning the damage liberalism was fated to do to the Catholic Church, the papacy, and Christianity as a whole. Riel prophesied no polemics against other religions, other than that a mass conversion of Jewish people to his form Christianity would soon occur. It is likely that the stance against liberalism would be similarly adopted against other religions that threatened the Exovedate.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: Due to the short-lived nature of the Exovedate, the cultural contact it had was largely neutral, save for an antagonistic relationship with the Canadian government and the support it afforded to the Métis.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: The Exovedate did engage in conflict with the Canadian government, but the battles and skirmishes all occurred within the sample region. The Exovedate never engaged in conflict outside the District of Saskatchewan.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: Membership is typically assigned by baptism. There was a separate ritual for the "redeeming" of a Protestant individual. A ritual where several priests would secretly pray, fast, and make alms over the course of a week would redeem the Protestant individual. Although redeemed, they were regarded as being in a lower class than traditional Catholics. Such an individual was barred from entering Churches except to attend low mass and communion would be given to them in the sacristy.

Reference: Riel, Louis. *The Collected Writings of Louis Riel / Les Ecrits Complets De Louis Riel*. Edited by Gilles Martel and George F. G. Stanley. Vol. 2. Edmonton, Alberta, Canada: The University of Alberta Press, n.d..

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Membership is typically assigned by baptism.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Religious professionals such as priests and bishops were required to proselytize, with priests also being required to participate in missionary work. Adherents were expected to proselytize, but not required to. Due to the focus on setting up and defending their new nation, the Exovedate did not spend much time proselytizing before their disbandment.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– I don't know

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: The Exovedate was the governmental body of the District of Saskatchewan during 1885, so the religion that underlyed it had full political support. They received no other political support.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not certain, during the reign of the Exovedate, if they financially compensated priests. The Exovedate would not have been against doing such a thing, but there is no evidence for one way, or the other.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: The Exovedate did plan to pay for religious infrastructure in the future, namely the building of churches. The group dissolved before any of the plans came to be realized.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: Louis Riel was the head of the Exovedate, and he was the prophet of the 'New World' religion. The spiritual head of the religion was a man named Ignace Bourget, the Bishop of Montreal during the time of Riel's prophethood. According to Riel, God had moved the papacy to the New World, where it now resided in Montreal with Bishop Bourget. It would later move to St. Vital in Manitoba, after a period of 457 years. During this period, Montreal was prophesized to suffer from a slow decline, due to being infected by 'liberalism.'

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

Notes: The religious hierarchy and the political hierarchy were separate, aside from Louis Riel. The hierarchical system of the Catholic Church was kept, and being part of the Exovedate was not equivalent to being a priest or bishop.

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

Notes: Given the influence of ultramontanism on Riel and the formation of the Exovedate, it is not impossible that at some point religious observance would have been enforced. However, during 1885 no such thing was enforced, or known to have even been discussed by the Exovedate.

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– Yes

Notes: Decisions made by the Exovedate during 1885 fall within the religious codes of Riel's prophecies and the Catholic Church.

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– No

Notes: There is no known examples of the Exovedate showing preferential treatment based on religion.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: When converted to the Catholicism of the Exovedate, adherents would have to give up any traditions, doctrines, etc. that did not align with the Exovedate and the prophecies of Louis Riel. Although it was allowed, and at times encouraged, to be done publicly, there was no requirement for it to be public. Some rituals around initiation and group membership were done in secret, without the knowledge of the non-Catholic individual being initiated. Several priests spend a week praying, fasting, and giving alms. The individual would then be informed that they were now Catholic, but would be subjected to certain restrictions on church visitation and receiving Communion.

Reference: Riel, Louis. *The Collected Writings of Louis Riel / Les Ecrits Complets De Louis Riel*. Edited by Gilles Martel and George F. G. Stanley. Vol. 2. Edmonton, Alberta, Canada: The University of Alberta Press, n.d..

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 20

Notes: Aside from the twenty men that made up the Exovedate, it is difficult to estimate how many adherents there were. This is partly due to a lack of data, the Exovedate was focused on establishing a recognized nation and the conflict with the Canadian government, so they did not conduct a census of adherents. The second issue is the blurred separation between the Catholic Church of the religion of the Exovedate. The Exovedate and all its members considered themselves to be Roman Catholic, and new members of the Eglise catholique, apostolique et vitale des Montagnes Lumineuses were confirmed as Catholics through baptism. This makes it difficult to categorize new adherents as following either Roman Catholicism, or the Catholicism of the Exovedate.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Exovedate never conducted a formal census of its adherents, or the size of the population that resided within its borders. It is estimated that 10,595 people lived in The District of Saskatchewan during this time, but it is not known how many of those people were adherents of the Exovedate.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: Scriptures would have included the Hebrew Bible, the New Testament, and the writings and oral prophecies of Louis Riel.

Reference: Riel, Louis. *The Collected Writings of Louis Riel*. Edited by Gilles Martel and George F. G.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Louis Riel wrote down most of his prophecies and visions, oftentimes in letters to Bishop Bourget, the would-be Pope of the New World. Aside from those, the Exovedate was derived from Roman Catholicism, so they held the Hebrew Bible and the New Testament to be holy scriptures.

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: Not all of the visions and prophecies of Louis Riel were written down. What was not written down, either by Riel or an Exovedate member, has been lost.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: The Hebrew Bible and the New Testament have their own narratives for their origins. Riel's prophecies, as told by himself, came to him from God. Starting from December 8, 1875, God would speak to Riel, other times sending Riel prophetic visions. He did so to instruct and assist Riel in his writing and proselytizing, making him the prophet of the New World.

Reference: Flanagan, Thomas. Louis 'david' Riel: 'prophet of the New World'. Toronto, Ontario, Canada: University of Toronto Press, n.d..

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: The Exovedate was disbanded before any monumental religious architecture could be constructed.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– Some public spaces

Notes: Present iconography came from the existing Catholic structures and population. This includes churches, crosses, and images of Catholic saints.

Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The afterlife consisted of Heaven and Hell. Those who lived in accordance with religious laws and morals would find themselves in Heaven after death. Those who lived in ways that went against religious laws and morals, those who espoused liberalism, and those who adhered to Protestantism would find themselves in Hell.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: Reincarnation was not believed to be a common occurrence, rather a notable exception. Louis Riel, founder and leader of the Exovedate, claimed to have reincarnated, living a past life as a Jewish man during the period of the Roman Empire.

Reference: Riel, Louis. *The Collected Writings of Louis Riel*, 1985.

https://books.google.com/books/about/The_collected_writings_of_Louis_Riel.html?hl=&id=rJf6zAEACAAJ.

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:

– No

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– No

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– I don't know

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The Exovedate believed in one God made of the Father, the Son, and the Holy Spirit.

- ↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No

- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes

- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Yes [specify]: God is seen as omniscient.

- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: God has knowledge that transcends time. In other word, God knew what events would occur in the future, including the end of the world.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - No
 - ↳ Through divination practices:
 - No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: God has spoken to non-religious specialists, although the act of God speaking to an individual typically elevates them from adherent to specialist. Louis Riel is an example of this, as he was elevated from adherent to prophet when God began to speak to him.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Certain events can be seen as being purposefully directed by God, and taken as signs or messages from God.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: The Exovedate held the belief that a human can become a saint, a spirit who is able to influence the world in a variety of ways. Saint Joseph was chosen as the special patron saint of the Metis.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: Saint are given certain domains, such as St. Joseph who was the Patron Saint of the Métis. However, it was not believed that this would restrict the knowledge of the Saint to the given domain.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Saints can, but only if it is in accordance with God's will.
- ↳ Human spirits can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can punish:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: The non-human supernatural beings are representatives of Heaven (God) and Hell (Satan). Heaven has angels, servants of God, and Hell has demons, servants of Satan.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - No
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - No
 - ↳ Organized hierarchically:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other organization for pantheon:
 - No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: God was believed to be able to monitor the thoughts and actions of any and every individual, and after death would judge if they lived their life in accordance with religious laws and with proper morals and ethics. It was also believed that in the year 4209 CE the Second Coming of Jesus Christ would occur, during which the Final Judgment would also occur. God would judge all living and dead people, rewarding some with Heaven, and punishing others to Hell.

Reference: Riel, Louis. The Collected Writings of Louis Riel / Les Ecrits Complets De Louis Riel. Edited by Gilles Martel and George F. G. Stanley. Vol. 2. Edmonton, Alberta, Canada: The University of Alberta Press, n.d..

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: Breaking a taboo (e.g. breaking a fast, vandalizing or damaging sacred spaces or objects) was not typically believed to be irredeemable or immediately met with punishment. Rather God would be displeased with the adherent, and they had to atone for what they had done or else they might face harsh judgement from God after their death.

↳ Food:

– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Murder of coreligionists was forbidden. Although there were death penalties for breaking certain divine laws, such as adultery, it was specified through the prophet Louis Riel that any execution done with negative emotions towards the criminal also constituted murder.

Reference: Riel, Louis. The Complete Writings of Louis Riel / Les Ecrits Complets De Louis Riel. Edited by Gilles Martel and George F. G. Stanley. Vol. 2. Edmonton, Alberta, Canada: The University of Alberta Press, n.d..

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: The murder of any person was forbidden.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: The murder of any person was forbidden.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: An adherent that committed adultery could face the death penalty.

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: Incest was largely forbidden. (1) If the father of a family passes away, leaving behind children to raise, forcing the eldest son, who must be unmarried and poor, to take over the role of the patriarch, the son was then allowed to ask for the hand of one his sisters in marriage. (2) If both the mother and the father pass away, the eldest son and daughter can marry, only if they finish raising their younger siblings. The eldest son is forbidden from taking other wives until after the family is raised. (3) An unmarried man can marry his widowed sister, but is required to look after her children as if they were his own. (4) If a women is unmarried at the age of 30, she is allowed to ask for her brother's hand in marriage. The brother must have less than 5 wives, as that is the maximum number of wives that was allowed for the average person.

Reference: Riel, Louis. *The Collected Writings of Louis Riel / Les Ecrits Complets De Louis Riel*. Edited by Gilles Martel and George F. G. Stanley. Vol. 2. Edmonton, Alberta, Canada: The University of Alberta Press, n.d..

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Premarital sex was frowned upon.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Punishment could be carried out by an angel, but was done so with at the behest of God.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– No

Notes: In cases of major punishment, God will communicate His reason. More often the individual has to reflect as to what the possible reasons for the punishment could be.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:
– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:
– No

↳ Other [specify]
– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Yes

Notes: A major precept was punishment in this life, as seen with the punishment of Pope Pius IX. It was believed that God would soon take the papacy away from Rome as a result of the Pope succumbing to the evils of liberalism.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
– I don't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
– I don't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
– I don't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
– Yes

↳ Other [specify]
– I don't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:
– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:
– Yes

- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - No
- ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
 - No
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
 - No
 - ↳ Other [specify]
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: The Exovedate held the belief that Christ would one day return to Earth, which would mark the beginning of the end times and the Final Judgment.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

↳ Coming on specified date:

– Yes

Notes: The Exovedate, following the revelations of the prophet Louis Riel, believed that the Second Coming of Jesus Christ would occur in the year 4209 C.E. The history of the world, past and future, was split into two symmetrical parts of 2333 years each. Thomas Flanagan breaks these parts of Riel's revelations further, into four sections: Jewish preparation, Roman fulfillment, French-Canadian preparation, and Métis fulfillment. The first 2333 years begins in 457 B.C.E. with the mission of the Ezra from the Hebrew Bible. This was the Jewish preparation. A period of 457 years pass and Christ is born in O C.E., marking the Roman fulfillment. 1876 years pass and Louis Riel is born in 1876 C.E., beginning the French-Canadian preparation. 457 years will pass, during which the papacy will transfer first from Rome to Bishop Bourget in Montreal, then from Montreal to St. Vital in 2333 C.E. Thus begins the Métis fulfillment, during which 1876 years will pass, and in 4209 C.E. the Second Coming is prophesied to occur.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: The messiah's purpose, that is the second coming of Christ, was believed to mark the day of the Last Judgement.

Notes: The Last Judgement was a belief that, after Christ returned to Earth for the second time, God would give one last, everlasting judgment on the souls of every person. This judgment would result in the individual being sent to Hell, or being able to reside with God in His kingdom of heaven.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Social norms come from Catholic scriptures, ultramontane beliefs, and the revelations of Louis Riel. The most notable differences in beliefs, that is to say beliefs that came from Riel and are 'unique' to the Exovedate, generally center around concerns of Mosaic Law. These include bringing back the

Mosaic Law, encouraging circumcision, Saturday Sabbath, and reformations for the modern family. Incest was allowed under a specific circumstance. The father must have passed away, and the eldest son must be in the position of taking care of his mother and siblings in the father's stead. If the son then neglects to marry, due to being poor and to better take care of his mother and siblings, then he should request the hand of one of his sisters, and the mother should allow it. Polygamy was allowed, where ordinary men could marry up to 5 wives. Kings (the religion of the Exovedate) could marry 15, their heir apparent could marry 8, the governor-general could marry 7, and a provincial lieutenant-governor could marry 6. Parental figures were barred from determining prospective candidates for their child's marriage. If two young people, of consenting age, are a suitable match and desire to be married, the parents are expected to favor said marriage. Clerical marriage between priests and nuns was allowed.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: Adherents were expected to be abstinent until marriage, and women were only allowed one husband.

↳ Monogamy (males):

– No

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– No

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Only at certain times of the year were certain foods forbidden.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents were expected to give monetary support to the church, as well as those in need.

To other in-group members:

– Yes

↳ To out-groups:

– Yes

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Examples of small-scale rituals would have been saying grace before eating, or praying in private. The length of this was not set and was up to the adherent.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The number of participants would have depended on the size of the community, ranging from a few dozen to a couple hundred at most.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 168

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

↳ Hair:
– No

↳ Dress:
– No

↳ Ornaments:
– No

↳ Archaic ritual language:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other:
– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:
– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:
– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:
– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: The Exovedate represented the church and The District of Saskatchewan, a new nation that would later become the province of Saskatchewan in modern Canada. Power was centralized around the Exovedate, with appointed officials. The head of state was Louis Riel.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: The Exovedate would have interacted with adherents, namely through the passing of laws.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The political members of the Exovedate interacted with the Canadian and American governments, but adherents outside of the political positions of the Exovedate would have now interaction with other institutional bureaucracies.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Field doesn't know

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Field doesn't know

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Métis, on behalf of the Exovedate, fought a few battles against the Royal Canadian Mounted Police. The first of which occurred on April 24, 1885. The last battle against the Exovedate occurred from May 9 - 15, 1885.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– I don't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: The Exovedate had a mix of Mosaic and New Testament laws, laws from Louis Riel's prophecies, and passed their own laws.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

Notes: The army was largely made up of Métis, Cree, and Assiniboines volunteer soldiers.

Reference: Beal, Bob, and Rod Macleod. "North-west Resistance". The Canadian Encyclopedia, July 8, 2021. <https://www.thecanadianencyclopedia.ca/en/article/north-west-rebellion>.

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– No

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– No

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: It was after the disbandment of the Exovedate that the former adherents were subjected to the military of the Canadian government.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: The Exovedate used French, English, and Latin.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The Exovedate used the Gregorian calendar.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Field doesn't know

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

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